

Time-dependent Quantum Mechanical Study of H₂ Chemisorption on W(001)

SUKARMA THAREJA and N. SATHYAMURTHY*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-208 016

Preliminary results of a time-dependent quantum mechanical study of the chemisorption dynamics of H₂ on W(001) using a model potential-energy surface are presented. In particular, vibrational excitation of H₂ is shown to enhance the probability of chemisorption.

STUDIES of state-to-state molecule-surface collisions have become possible in recent years due to a combination of ultra-high vacuum technology, molecular beams and laser selection/detection of molecules in specific vibrational states¹. Different theoretical approaches have been used to model the collision problem². Unfortunately no reliable potential energy surface (PES) is available for any 'real' system. *Ab initio* surfaces of the quality known for a few elementary atom-diatom systems will probably not become available for molecule-surface interactions for a long time to come. Yet, Wolken and coworkers³ started investigating molecule-surface collisions using London-Eyring-Polanyi-Sato (LEPS) surfaces using classical trajectories more than a decade ago. Quantum mechanically, the time-dependent approach has been attempted enthusiastically for a few systems⁴. For example, Jackson and Metiu⁵ investigated the dissociative chemisorption of H₂ on Ni and Halstead and Holloway⁶ H₂ on Cu. As a part of our investigations of molecule-surface collisions, we present here preliminary results of our time-dependent quantal calculations on the chemisorption of H₂ on W(001) using a model LEPS surface.

Results and Discussion

We have restricted the geometry of H₂ to lie parallel in its approach to the atop site of the rigid W(001) surface so that the dynamics is restricted to two coordinates: Z , the center-of-mass separation of H₂ from the surface, and r , the vibrational coordinate of the former.

The dynamics of the system was studied by numerically solving the time-dependent Schrödinger equation,

$$H\Psi = (-\hbar^2/i)\partial\Psi/\partial t \quad (1)$$

where, the Hamiltonian H in (Z, r) coordinates is given by

$$H = (-\hbar^2/2M)\nabla_Z^2 - (\hbar^2/2\mu)\nabla_r^2 + V(Z, r) \quad (2)$$

where, M is the mass of H₂ ($=2m_H$) and μ its reduced mass ($=m_H/2$). The wave function Ψ at time $t=0$ was taken to be a product of the Morse oscillator wave function for H₂ in its ground ($v=0$) or the first excited ($v=1$) vibrational state and a gaussian centered at $Z_0=8.0$ a.u. moving with an average translational energy of 0.52 eV.

$$\Psi(t=0) = \phi(Z) X_v(r) \quad (3)$$

$$\phi(Z) = (2\pi\delta^2)^{-1/4} \exp[-(Z-Z_0)^2/4\delta^2 - ik_0Z] \quad (4)$$

$$X_0(r) = [\alpha/\Gamma(2s)]^{1/2} (2\sigma)^s [\exp\{-s\alpha(r-r_0)\}] \times [\exp\{-\sigma \exp\{-\alpha(r-r_0)\}\}] \quad (5)$$

where,

$$\sigma = (2\mu D)^{1/2}/\alpha\hbar \text{ and } s = \sigma - (1/2)$$

Similarly,

$$X_1(r) = N_1 F_1 F_2 F_3 \quad (6)$$

with

$$N_1 = (1/M_1)^{1/2}$$

$$M_1 = [1/\alpha A^{(A-s)}][\Gamma(A-3) + \Gamma(A-2)]$$

$$A = b + 1; \quad b = (8\mu D)^{1/2}/\alpha\hbar^2 - 1$$

$$F_1 = \exp(-DF); \quad F_2 = F^{(A-s)/2}; \quad F_3 = z - (A-2)$$

$$z = AF; \quad D = A/2; \quad F = \exp[-\alpha(r-r_0)]$$

We have used the LEPS PES as formulated by McCreery and Wolken³ with a Sato parameter $\Delta = -0.08$. The potential-energy contours (Fig. 1) reveal an activation barrier of 0.54 eV for adsorption and a chemisorption well depth of 1.26 eV, relative to isolated H₂ and W.

The wave function was time evolved using the explicit method⁷ with a time step of 0.26925×10^{-16} s. The Laplacian of Ψ during the time evolution was evaluated using a 3-point finite difference method. For the dynamics involving H₂ ($v=0$), we used a 76×55 grid with $\Delta Z = 0.16$ a.u. and $\Delta r/2 = 0.08$ a.u. and for $v=1$, a 64×64 grid was used with $\Delta Z = 0.16$ a.u. and $\Delta r/2 = 0.078$ a.u.

Temporal evolution of Ψ is illustrated in Figs. 2 and 3 with the aid of three-dimensional perspective

* INBA Research Fellow (1989-91).

drawings of $\Psi^*\Psi$ in $(Z, r/2)$ space. It is clear that for $\nu=0$, the wave packet has spread sufficiently in 3600 time steps, separating into a portion caught in the chemisorption zone and a portion retreating

Fig 1. Potential-energy contours for H_2-W in $(Z, r/2)$ coordinates.

into the entry channel. The chemisorption probability (P_C) was evaluated as

$$P_C = \int_{Z=0}^{Z^*} \int_{r=0}^{r_{\max}} \Psi^*\Psi \, dr dZ / \int_{Z=0}^{Z_{\max}} \int_{r=0}^{r_{\max}} \Psi^*\Psi \, dr dZ \quad (7)$$

with $Z^*=5.50$ a.u. and plotted as a function of t in Fig. 4. It is clear that the time evolution is nearly over and $P_C=0.40$. Similar plot of $P_C(t)$ for $\nu=1$ yields $P_C=0.45$, thus establishing the vibrational enhancement of chemisorption.

A closer examination of the plots in Figs. 2 and 3 reveals that the wave packet has spread significantly to large r values, characteristic of dissociative chemisorption. Some authors used $r > 2r_0$ (where r_0 is the equilibrium bond distance of H_2) as the criterion to identify dissociation. We could easily partition the configuration space accordingly and compute the probability of dissociative chemisorption, P_D . Since the initial wave packet samples a range of translational energies for H_2 relative to W , our results correspond to an average P_C , $\langle P_C \rangle$. In principle, we can carry out a deconvolution of $\langle P_C \rangle$ and obtain E_{trans} dependence of P_C . Such a study is presently being pursued.

Fig. 2. Plots of $|\Psi|^2$ in $(Z, r/2)$ space for a model $H_2(\nu=0)+W(001)$ collision at time steps $NT=0, 1800$ and 3600 for $\langle E_{\text{trans}} \rangle = 0.52$ eV.

Fig. 3. Same as Fig. 2 for H_2 ($v=1$) at $NT=0, 2400$ and 4200 .

Fig. 4 $\langle P_C \rangle$ as a function of t with each time step = 0.26925×10^{-16} s.

A more detailed examination of the sensitivity of the dynamics to features of the PES and the classical dynamics, particularly from the viewpoint of fractals⁸, are currently in progress.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.T.) would like to thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi for a Research Fellowship.

This study was supported in part by a grant under the INDO-US sub-commission. The authors thank Dr. J. W. Gadzuk for inspiring discussions.

References

1. "Dynamics of Gas-Surface Interactions", eds. G. BRNDEK and U. VALBUSA, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1982.
2. R. B. GERBER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1987, 87, 29.
3. J. MCCREERY and G. WOLKEN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, 63, 2340; 1976, 65, 181; 1977, 66, 231; *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1976, 3, 478; G. WOLKEN and J. MCCREERY, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1978, 54, 33.
4. R. B. GERBER, R. KOSLOFF and M. BERMAN, *Computer Phys. Rep.*, 1986, 5, 59.
5. B. JACKSON and H. METIU, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1987, 86, 1027.
6. D. HALSTEAD and S. HOLLOWAY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1988, 88, 7197.
7. V. MOHAN and N. SATHYAMURTHY, *Computer Phys. Rep.*, 1988, 7, 215.
8. "Fractals: Form, Chance and Dimension", B. B. Mandelbrot, W. H. Freeman and Co., San Francisco, 1977.